

Panchayat Samithis in Anantapur District

B NAGABHUSHANA
Lecturer in History,
Government College (A)
Anantapur

Abstract

Local Self governance is a cornerstone of a vibrant democracy. Anantapur district was part of Bellary district up to 1882. Local Boards Act IV of 1871 created Fund Boards. In the district three Fund Circles (Tadipatri, Gooty, Anantapur, Alur and Adoni) created. The Local Boards Act V of 1884 created District Boards, Taluk Boards and Unions. The Taluk Boards in the district were constituted in October 1886. Panchayat Samithis and Zilla Parishads Act 1959 created Gram panchayats at village level, Panchayat Samithis at Block level and Zilla Parishads at district level. This abstract focuses on the middle level panchayats and decentralized system. The middle level panchayats in the district played a crucial role in coordinating and implementing developmental activities at Taluk level. The Panchayat Samithis tried to address the needs and challenges of the diverse communities within their jurisdiction.

Key words: Local governance, Taluk level administration, block level governance, Community engagement, rural empowerment.

The Madras Local Boards Act V of 1884 enabled for the constitution of a District Board at the District level, a Taluk Board at the Taluk or Divisional level and a Union Board for a village or a group of villages. Taluk Boards were formed for each Taluk or a group of Taluks with a president and not less than twelve members. They were partly appointed and partly elected by the members of the Union Boards or by the tax payers themselves. Their term of office was three years. The Taluk Boards jurisdiction coincided with that of the revenue divisional officers who were made ex- officio members and presidents of these Boards.

Taluk Boards in Anantapur District:

In Anantapur district Taluk Boards were formed in October 1886¹. In 1895-96 the Taluk Boards of Penukonda and Anantapur were reconstituted the former with Penukonda, Hindupur, Madakasira and Dharmavaram Taluks and the latter with Anantapur and the newly formed Kalyandurg Taluk. Consequently, the Hindupur Board ceased to function. The Local Boards Act 1898 was amended as a result which the Governor could nominate a non – official as the president of a Local Board. By 1889 there were five non official members in the District Board elected from the Taluk Boards of Gooty, Anantapur and Hindupur. Three were ex- officio members and 12 (three official and nine non- official) were nominated. Till 1920 there

was no any significant change in the functioning of Boards. In the district, except the changes in the jurisdiction of Taluk Boards, an increase in the number of elected representatives and the creation of more unions².

About the year 1900 tax rates were modified and the Local Boards Act was amended and formed a procedure for the removal of the president, vice president or any member from office. In the year 1902-03, the presidents of the respective Boards were declared to be members of the Boards over which they presided.

The Royal Commission on Decentralization published its report in 1909. The report emphasized that there should be elected majorities in both the Taluk and District Boards and village panchayats should be completely elective. The number of members constituting the Taluk Boards of Anantapur and Gooty was raised from 13 to 15 in 1909-10. In 1911 the Kadiri Taluk was added to Anantapur district. The Taluk Boards were also regrouped. They were located at Anantapur, Gooty, Dharmavaram and Penukonda. Their number was raised to four in the place of existing three. The Penukonda and Dharmavaram Taluk Boards had a strength of fifteen each, while Anantapur and Gooty had a strength of 13 each. Elective strength of Taluk Boards was raised from 1/3 to 1/2 in 1912. With this change the total number of elected seats in all of Taluk Boards in Anantapur district became 30.

In 1914, for the first time a non-official was appointed as the president of the Anantapur Taluk Board. In 1918 the Government of India passed a resolution that the local bodies should have a substantial elected majority and the system of nomination should be restricted only to secure the necessary representation of minorities. During the year 1919-20 the principle of election was employed on a large scale in the local bodies. In Taluk Boards 2/3 of the strength was made elective and the number of elected seats on the district boards were raised from sixteen to twenty-four. In 1919 a non-official vice president was appointed to the District Board and non-official presidents to the Gooty and Penukonda Taluk Boards. In the year 1920 the strength of the Gooty Taluk Board was raised from 15 to 24. To make provision for the representation of depressed classes and minorities and Anantapur Taluk Board was given the right of electing its president in the same year³.

Next important landmark development in the local self-government was the passing of the Local Boards Act XIV of 1920. It enhanced local bodies resources, powers strength and proportion of elected members. Further, this act gave an independent status to different classes of local boards. The strength of the union boards was fixed at a maximum of fifteen and a minimum of seven, that of the Taluk Board at a maximum of 24 and a minimum of twelve, and that of the district board was at a maximum of 52 and a minimum of 24 respectively. In all these boards the proportion of elected members should be three- fourths of their total strength. Their tenure was three years. As per the act the District Collector and the Revenue Divisional Officers seized to be presidents and ex officio members. The president of the District and the Taluk Boards became ex officio members of the district and Taluk boards respectively. Taluk Boards presidents also became ex officio members of the district board.

In Anantapur district, the Local Boards Act of 1920 came into force from 1st April 1921. Consequently, the number of elected and ex-officio members of the Board was raised from 24 to 28 while the number of nominated members reduced from 12 to 8. The Board president was a nominated non official and there was no direct election to the District Board. The strength of the Anantapur District Board in 1923 – 24 was fixed at 36 consisting of 28 elected and 8 nominated members. In the next year, the strength of the District Board remained same but there were 24 elected members, 4 ex – officio and 8 nominated members. In 1926 the Anantapur district Board was allowed to elect its president. Diwan Bahadur P. Kesava Pillai was not only the first non – official nominated president but also the first elected president.

In July 1922 the reconstituted Taluk Boards came into being. There were four Taluk Boards in the district viz., Hindupur and Madakasira Taluks and Dharmavaram covering Dharmavaram and Kadiri Taluks, Penumonda extending over Penukonda, Gooty including Gooty and Tadipatri Taluks and Anantapur comprising Anantapur and Kalyandurg taluks. The members of these Taluk Boards were directly elected. The jurisdiction of these Taluk Boards corresponded to the revenue divisions of the district. The Dharmavaram Taluk Board president was nominated. All other board presidents were elected⁴

The Local Boards (Amendment) Act XI of 1930 enabled the office of president elected and brought about provincialization of services. The new act abolished the system of nominations, extended the franchise to every income tax assessee and introduced the direct election. Women were allowed to contest in elections. Further, provision was made for the removal of chairmen and presidents by a vote of no – confidence. As per the new act, nine Taluk Boards were created, one for each Revenue Taluk. The strength of the Anantapur District Board underwent a change.

Some of the significant changes made after 1930 were abolition of all Taluk Boards in 1934. Taluk Boards main functions were transferred to District Boards along with their assets and liabilities. The term of office of all District Boards along with Anantapur district Board was extended up to July 1953 by legislation. Since then, elections to the District Board were suspended till the closer of them in 1959. Between 1953 to 1959 District Collectors functioned as Special Officers of District Boards. Zillaparishads were formed in the place of District Boards under the Andhra Pradesh Panchayat Samithis and Zilla Parishads Act 1959.⁵

Panchayat Samithis:

In accordance with the recommendations of the Balwantarai Mehta Committee, the Andhra Pradesh Panchayat Samithis and Zill Parishads Act 1959 enabled for the constitution of Zilla parishads at the district level and Panchayat Samithis at Block level. As per the recommendations of the Mehta team, stage – I and stage – II blocks came into being in Anantapur district along with others. There were 8 stages – I blocks, one stage – II block, a pre – extension block and two C D blocks in the district by March 1959. Earlier in 1958 Putlur was constituted into a Stage – I block and Rayadurg into a pre – Extension block. In 1959, two new pre-extension blocks were constituted at Tanakal and Kottacheruvu. As per the Mehta committee recommendations, on 1st July 1958, 20 ad hock panchayat Samithis at the rate of one for each district were constituted⁶. In Anantapur district one such Samithi was constituted at Kodiganahalli. The Blocks in the

district were de limited and made contiguous with the revenue Taluks, as per the blocks de limitation order 1964. A list of the existing panchayat Samithis blocks with their jurisdiction is given below.

Panchayat Samithis in Anantapur District

S No.	Name of the Panchayat Samithi	Full revenue Firka comprising the Samithi	Revenue Firka partly comprising the Samithi
1	Singanamala	Singanamala Firka (Full) Narpala Firka (full) Anantapur Firka (part)	Anantapur Firka (Part) Podaralla Jantaluru Siddarampuram Siddampeta Reddipalli Upparapalli Chiyyedu Chinnarayanapalli Itikalapalli Bukkarayasamudram Govindapalli Anantapur Rural
2	Kudair	1 Bukkacherla Firka (full) 2 Kudair Firka (full) 3 Anantapur (part)	Kodimi Rachanapalli Somaladoddi Taticherla Kakkalapalli Katiganikalva Papampeta Raphadu Gangulakunta Narayanapuram Kandukuru Shro. Janagalapalli
3	Tadipatri	Yadiki Firka (full) Tadipatri (full) (except Tadipatri Municipal town) Peddapappuru Firka(full) Putlur Firka(full) Yellanuru Firka (full)	
4	Gooty	Gooty Firka (full) Thimanacherla Firka (full) Pamidi Firka(full) Nagasamudram Firka (full)	
5	Uravakonda	Uravakonda Firka (full) Vajrakarur Firka (full)	
6	Dharmavaram	Dharmavaram Firka (Except Dharmavaram town) Tadimarri Firka (full)	
7	C K Palli	Medapuram Firka (full) Kanaganapalli Firka (full) Ramagiri Firka (full)	
8	Kalyandurg	Beluguppa Firka (full) Kalyandurg Firka (full)	
9	Kambudur	Kambadur	

		Bramhasamudram Firka (full) Kundurpi Firka (full)	
10	Rayadurg	Rayadurg Firka (full) (except Rayadurg Municipal town) Hirehal Firka (full)	
11	Kanekal	Kanekal Fika (full) Bommanhal Firka (full)	
12	Penukonda	Roddam Firka (full) Penukonda Firka (full) Bukkapatnam Firka (full) Kottachervu Firka (full)	
13	Madakasira	Madakasira Firka (full) Hemavathi Firka (full) Rollan Firka (full)	
14	Kodegenahalli	Hindupur Firka (full) (Except Hindupur Municipal town) Parigi Firka (full) Gorantla Firka (full) Chillamathur Firka (full)	
15	Kadiri East	Dhaniyanichervu Firka (full) Tanakallu Firka (full) Kadiri Firka (part)	Kadiri Firka (part) Obulapalli Kurli Udumulakurthi Talupula Bandlapalli Noothanakalva Obulareddipalli Puligundlapalli Vepanipeta Peddannavaripalli Gantlapenta Thummalabyulu Godduvelagala Chalamakuntlapalli Pandulakunta Alampur Kadirikuntlapalli Kadiri Rural Kadiri Town Kamathampalli Maridivarigondi Jagannapeta Allugundu Mothukapalli Kowlepalli
16	Kadiri West	Gunjepalli Firka (full) Nallamada Firma (full) Muhammadabad Firka(full) Kadiri Firka (full)	Kadiri Firka (Part) Kalasamudram Erradoddi Shro – Chippalamadugu Shro – Kondamanayanipalyem

Source: Anantapur District Gazetteer

The Andhra Pradesh panchayat Samithis and Zillaparishads Act 1959 (and subsequently the Andhra Pradesh Gram panchayats Act 1964 and amendments to these principal acts and rules and regulations made there under) enabled the constitution of the three – tier panchayat Raj set up in the state. As per this act there emerged three different institutions, viz., 1. Village/ Gram panchayats at the bottom of the hierarchy. 2. Panchayat Samithis at the intermediary level which coincided with the corresponding revenue Taluks and erstwhile community development blocks and 3. Zillaparishads at the district level. It is very clear that various program functions and activities entrusted to these boards would clear that the three tier panchayat raj institutions were designed to play their role as the catalyst of change and harbingers of rural development⁷.

The introduction of the principle of democratic de centralization through three tier panchayat raj institutions in 1959 gave a greater importance a sense of urgency and priority to the significant task of rural development. Efficient local leadership popular involvement local knowledge and public cooperation made the decentralized democratic institutions at grassroots level to strive their best in expediting the rural development in the relatively backward district of Anantapur. Further, local bodies were obliged to become agents of change. The existing administrative system based on district and Taluks and erstwhile community development blocks that came into being after 1952 enabled the demarcation of jurisdictions of Zillaparishads, Panchat Samithis and Gram panchayats that came into being on the basis of Andhra Pradesh panchayat Samithis and Zillaparishads Act 1959, and Andhra Pradesh Gram panchayats Act 1964. With these legislative enactments there came into being in Anantapur district. The three-tier panchayat raj system, Zillaparishads at the district level and 16 Panchayat Samithis that existed with the areas covered by 16 revenue Taluks and 740 village panchayats (18 notified and 722 non notified panchayats)⁸. For proper understanding of the panchayat raj institutions in the Anantapur district, an analysis of their organizational set up and powers and functions is absolutely necessary.

Under the panchayat raj system that existed in the Anantapur district during the period between 1959 to 1985, the institutional set up at the intermediary level, viz., the panchayat Samithies were very prominent. At the district level Zillaparishads were made only the supervisory and coordinating bodies. And the Grampanchayats existed at the bottom of the institutional hierarchy.

There were 16 panchayat Samithis in Anantapur district. Panchayat Samithis constituted the second tier in the panchayat raj institutional set in the district. Panchayat Samithis were most important local bodies in view of rural development. In spite of their important position and role expecting rural development, the panchayat Samithis were not completely popular in composition but consisted of ex officio members as well all sarpanches in the Samithi area were its ex officio members and six members were coopted but they were representing the women from the scheduled casts and schedule tribe. In 1978 as a process to change in the concerned statute, the predominantly ex officio composition of the panchayat Samithis underwent a radical change. As a result of these change, the panchayat Samithi was to consist of not less than 20 but not more than 30 members. The total strength of the Samithi was to be decided on the basis of population of the Samithi.

For electing the members of the Samithi, the Samithi area was divided into as many areas –wards as the number to be elected by registered voters in the wards – areas. Panchayat Samithi seats were reserved for the scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. The number of seats reserved to the scheduled casts and scheduled tribes were based on the proportion to the size of their population. Thus, the panchayat Samithi consisted of elected members, members of the legislative assembly constituency covered by Samithi and members of the legislative council⁹. The members of the panchayat Samithi had to elect two women from among the registered voters¹⁰. One person should be elected from cultural and linguistic minority¹¹, and three persons belonging to the backward classes¹². Apart from this, panchayat Samithis also composed of some ex officio members as the Director of District Cooperative Central Bank representing Samithi area, the chairman of the primary agricultural Development Bank, President of the Primary Cooperative Marketing Society, if any in the Samithi area.

Eligible registered voters in the Samithi area used to elect the president of samithi¹³. Both the president and members were elected for a period of five years. Sections 18 to 21 (vide the Andhra Pradesh Panchayat Samithis and Zillaparishads Act 1959) clarified the powers and functions of the panchayat Samithis. Numerous development functions of the panchayat Samithis related to education, health and sanitation, social welfare, women welfare, emergency welfare, agriculture, animal husbandry, fisheries, collection of statistics and self-help programs. These development functions of panchayat Samithis proved the pivotal role and significance of panchayat Samithis in rural development. Above said development functions of economic and social character were indeed impressive. As far as functional responsibilities of the panchayat Samithis has to be viewed from the angle of Samithis position in the financial spear.

Standing committees in the panchayat Samithis played a very important role in its functions. There were five standing committees dealing with such specific subjects, they were 1 Development 2 Education 3 Social welfare 4 Public works and 5 finance. Each one of these committees covered various items of works. In the working of panchayat Samithis standing committees played significant role.

Panchayat Samithi president convened meetings and presided over the same and conducted proceedings of the Samithi meetings.¹⁴ Samithi president had the rights to access all the papers and documents of Samithi. He was assisted by the vice president who was elected by members of the Samithi from among themselves. Block Development officer acted as Chief Executive Officer of panchayat Samithi. To ensure the implementation of resolutions of the panchayat Samithi and its standing committees, the president could exercise administrative control over the Block Development officer. In case of any emergency, the Samithi president could in consultation with the Block Development Officer, president could execute any work or perform any other act which in his opinion was necessary for welfare of people, but president had to report all such acts to the panchayat Samithi later.

Balwant Rai Mehta team emphasized the need of decentralization of democratic bodies at grass root level for accomplishing the goals of rural development. For achieving the objectives and goals of rural development depends on properly trained and development oriented personal¹⁵. A P Panchayat Samithis and Zillaparishads Act 1959 explain at length the powers and functions of the Block Development Officers, other officials and staff and creation of posts of officers and employees of the Samithi. The Block Development officer was the Chief Executive Officer of the Panchayat Samithi. He was the head of administrative set up of Samithi. Block Development officer was assisted by a team of technical officers known as the extension officers¹⁶. They were subject specialists in charge of such subjects as education, health, agriculture, animal husbandry, cooperation, and cottage industries etc., These extension officers were entrusted with developmental programs. The extension officer's nature of work enabled them to be in a touch with people in rural areas. The village level worker was a very important functionary connected with the implementation of development program. The number of his duties and nature of work made him a multipurpose extension worker.

Block Development officer was responsible for implementing all resolutions of panchayat Samithi and its standing committees. He was in charge of preparing the annual budget and administrative report. Block Development officer had to go on tour to inspect the program and progress achieved in implementing development projects. He was the main link between the Samithi and the external agencies of the government.

Panchayat Samithi has the decentralized democratic body, it's success or failure largely depended on the caliber and competence of the Block Development Officer and his team. It is need less to emphasize that the kind of administration provided by the Block Development officer and his team would play an important role in successful implementation of development scheme and program at the panchayat Samithi level. In the three-tier institutional hierarchy of panchayat raj bodies, panchayat Samithis played an important role this could be established with the kind of institutional assistance. They were providing to play an important role as the instrument of rural development. In the panchayat Samithi there were standing committees exactly similar to their counterparts at the Zillaparishad level in the functional responsibility also there was close similarity. For example, in sphere of rural development both the Zillaparishad and panchayat Samithi were assigned with definite and positive roles. And standing committees¹⁷ were very formidable instruments of aid and oversee the implementation of developmental program and activities on which ultimately the success or failure of the cause of rural development would depend.

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